

METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS IN FUTURE MUSIC TEACHERS

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Abstract: In this thesis, the importance of communicative skills in the professional activity of future music teachers, their place in the educational process and development strategies are considered. Modern pedagogical methods, innovative technologies and practical training are discussed for the effective development of communication skills in future teachers. The thesis also presents the influence of communicative skills in the field of music education, the improvement of interaction between the teacher and the student, and the necessary measures and recommendations to increase the effectiveness of the educational process.

Keywords: Communicative skills, pedagogical methods, innovative technologies, educational process, professional development, methodology.

Introduction.

Communication skills of teachers play an important role in the modern education process. Especially for music education teachers, these skills are of great importance in imparting music-related knowledge and experiences to students. This article examines the methodology of developing communicative skills in future music education teachers.

The importance of communication skills

Communication skills are necessary for a music education teacher to effectively communicate with students, analyze musical works and explain them correctly, convey performance techniques and communicate with the audience. Through these skills, the teacher can develop students' abilities and increase their interest in the art of music in their pedagogical activities.

Ways to develop communication skills

The following methods can be used to develop communicative skills in future music education teachers:

1. Dialogic approach to training: Question-and-answer training should be organized to encourage students to be active and to encourage communication and exchange of ideas among them. Mutual relations are formed between the teacher and the students by holding debates and discussions in music lessons.

2. Comparative analysis and discussions: Students should be given the opportunity to listen to different musical works and analyze them, as well as create conditions for them to freely express their opinions. In this process, the

teacher talks about different aspects of music and directs the students to evaluate and analyze it.

3. Training and practical training: Special training aimed at forming communication and speech skills should be organized for future teachers. These can take the form of role plays, discussion clubs and presentations. Through these trainings, future teachers develop the ability to communicate with students during music lessons, answer their questions and convey the necessary information to them.

4. Development of music listening and analysis skills: Music listening and analysis play an important role in improving the communication skills of music education teachers. By analyzing the works of different genres, the possibilities of correctly explaining their content, performance style and other aspects to the students will expand.

5. Use of music technologies and multimedia: The use of various technological tools in music education also develops communicative skills. The use of multimedia in communication with students, visual analysis of musical works, enlivens and increases the effectiveness of communication between the teacher and students.

Composition of communicative competence

The communicative competence developed in the future music education teacher consists of the following components:

1. Speech culture: Music teacher's speech should have a specific culture. This includes, among other things, the correct formation of speech, the appropriate use of musical terms, maintaining logic in interpretation, and expressing in a way that can engage the students.

2. Emotional expression: In music lessons, it is important for the teacher to use emotional expression in his speech and actions to attract students to feel and understand the emotional content of musical works.

3. Communication skills: It is necessary for the teacher to communicate openly with students, listen to their opinions and exchange ideas with them. It helps students to demonstrate their abilities through interaction.

Conclusion:

The development of communication skills in future music education teachers is important for their success in their pedagogical activities. The methods and approaches presented in this article help to organize effective communication between teachers and students, to increase interest in music and to conduct music

education at a high level. Therefore, the development of communicative skills should remain an integral part of the music education process.

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